

DESCRIPTION OF MODERN METHODS OF MARKETING RESEARCH

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Abstract. *This article examines manufacturers depending on the market situation, the nature of the goals and objectives and the established strategy, what marketing research and how to carry it out, what human and financial resources to use, what to do independently, what research to order from abroad needs to be decided what it's good to do it. To save human and financial resources and achieve high results in marketing research, it is necessary to conceptually see how this problem will look in the future.*

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Introduction. To obtain data in any scientific research, two sources of information are used - primary and secondary. Secondary sources are available data that should always be examined first. In most cases, this data will be collected for purposes other than the intended research areas. Therefore, it is necessary to collect them with new data or fill them with primary data. The difference between the sources of information has led to the existence of two different concepts - desk research and field research. As mentioned above, an office survey is conducted prior to an out-of-office survey to collect secondary data. Because the necessary information will be available, even if it needs to be systematized and filled in. In addition, these studies will allow you to accurately determine what information should be obtained in the course of an investigation or experiment. It also saves time and money as printed materials are relatively easy to obtain and use correctly as a source of information.

A cabinet study begins with a review of the firm's own report. While the relevant departments are responsible for maintaining the records, the marketing research department must ensure an adequate level of harmonization of the reports and thus create a database for the firm. The reporting documents from which such basic information can be obtained should cover the following areas of activity.

Purchase (reservation rate, utilization rate, etc.).

Production (volume of production, materials, labor, transportation and storage of goods, their handling, packaging and packaging, overhead costs, use of equipment, etc.).

Personnel (labor cost, staff turnover, labor productivity levels, absenteeism for no good reason).

Marketing (sales promotion costs, administrative costs, information on specific markets and brands, etc.).

Sales (by value of individual products, share of profit, volume of orders, type of sales channels or customers, by sales region or agent).

Finance (balance sheet data).

Qualitative research can help identify the most important needs that can be commercialized. The hallmark of qualitative research is the application of a more inductive research philosophy than a deductive one. In addition, qualitative research is more creative and

requires not only intelligence but also intuition from the researcher. In international practice, there are five main methods of qualitative research:

a comprehensive interview that allows you to conduct an in-depth study, identify new aspects of the problem and give accurate and meaningful assessments;

Focus group interviews - its growing popularity in quality commercial research is due to direct, real-time conversations with real customers, who can track them using a hidden video camera;

included observation, in which the researcher openly or secretly participates in everyday life for a sufficiently long period of time, observes the events taking place, listens to what is being said, asks questions related to the research task. This method makes it possible to more effectively assess the real quality of an innovative product and the range of innovative services provided;

situational analysis, based on its methodological focus, makes beliefs specific to work in the field of psychology;

projection techniques. This method is used when focus group members are asked to express their feelings, thoughts and desires about a new product.

In addition to the firm's internal materials listed above, the researcher also uses a large number of additional sources of information. They can be grouped into the following main categories:

Official data sources (local and foreign).

Publications from universities and non-profit research organizations.

Industry trade association publications.

Academic, professional and commercial journals.

Internet materials, results of surveys in social networks;

Commercial research reports.

Research methodology. During the research process, a systematic approach, abstract logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and sampling observation methods were used.

Analysis and results. When using printed materials as a source of information, it is important to determine by what method they were collected and systematized. If the methods do not match, there is no need to analyze them directly. It should also only be used if the researcher has complete confidence in the veracity of the information. If the main problem is not solved even after reviewing all printed sources of information, then research outside the office is a prerequisite. These areas include:

advertising research (analysis of the effectiveness of advertising, study of advertising media, analysis of the use of media channels, determination of the size of the consumer audience);

consumer research (research of factors that determine consumer choice and preferences);

analysis of the effectiveness of the type (set) of the distributor (comparison of alternative components of the distribution type, methods of handling the load, etc.);

research of consumer characteristics (analysis of the idea of a new product, testing a product with the involvement of a consumer, identifying possible consumption and classification of consumers of this product, etc.).

Primary data can be collected by one of three methods: observation, experiment and sample research, as well as through their combined use. Observation is the simplest method and, in most cases, gives satisfactory results. The essence of this method is to observe the processes associated

with the studied factors. An example of this is measuring the flow of shoppers into a store, which is one of the main planning methods for commercial buildings.

Observation methods depend on the level of knowledge of the observer about his work and on how fairly he approaches the process. The limitation of this method is its hidden nature. Because observation shouldn't have a negative impact on the minds of buyers. In addition, the appearance often does not reveal the internal motivation of the buyer.

It is possible to control during the experiment. The experiment is cheaper than the method of choice. The main disadvantage of the experimental method is the inability to restore normal customer behavior in the laboratory. In most cases, such difficulties are solved by conducting an experiment in vivo. For example, packaging can be obtained by placing experimental samples on store shelves. Learning just one variable can be very costly and time consuming. The reason is to test a large number of variables. For example, when examining a package, you can determine the name, color, size, shape, informational value and overall effect that affect it individually. Currently, there are methods such as the method of Latin squares, the method of factor analysis.

The most common method for obtaining primary data is sampling. Teaching methods are determined by three factors, depending on time and money constraints:

1. The contingent of requested persons.
2. Means of communication with the requested persons.
3. With the nature of the required information and methods of obtaining it.

In theory, the most ideal way to collect primary data is to conduct a census of all persons to be studied. In practice, it is almost impossible to hold such an event.

After the interviewees have been identified using a sample, the researcher communicates with them using the following methods: personal interview, questionnaire by mail and telephone interview. We'll begin our review of these methods with a telephone interview. The main disadvantage of this method is that the owners of personal telephones constitute a certain group of the population. However, earlier this factor received more attention. Nowadays, telephone interviews are becoming more and more important for fast and active investigation. Telephone interviews are useful when researching soft drink markets. A telephone interview must be short and clear to be effective. Otherwise, the interview may confuse the respondent and the interview may end prematurely.

The advantage of doing a survey by mail is that you can effortlessly connect with any family and entrepreneur. It also prevents the interviewer from altering the survey results through no fault of their own. However, the main disadvantage of this method is the slow response rate for requests sent by mail. If the answer is 50%, this is a very good result. Due to the shortcomings of telephone and mail requests, face-to-face interviews remain the most common and acceptable method. Using experienced interviews increases the percentage of positive responses to research. The interviewer's ability to explain all complex issues increases the accuracy of the research and also provides an opportunity to gather additional information. The main disadvantage of conducting a personal interview is the high cost and lack of experienced interviewers. However, many problems can be minimized by properly compiling the questionnaire. Most of the standard questionnaires contain not only questions, but also alternative answers. any questionnaire requires four basic elements. First, not every survey can be anonymous. Hence, they will have a name and a serial number. In addition, when an interviewer conducts an interview, it is necessary to indicate the time and place of the interview, as well as the interview number and signature. Secondly, each questionnaire must contain registration information about the requested persons. This information

is obtained partly through survey, partly through observation and includes: age, gender, social status, occupation of the head of the family, marital status, family composition, level and nature of education. name and address of the defendant, Information about whether you are a tenant or landlord, the availability of real estate, the provision of durable goods, although not mandatory, is considered useful information. While information about a respondent's income is important, for many it is an invasion of privacy.

Thirdly, the questionnaire must contain control questions. This is to ensure that the respondent follows the sequence of his answers and that the questionnaire is completed as instructed. Fourthly, the questionnaire should provide information necessary to solve the problem under study.

After the collected data is systematized, summarized and analyzed, the results and recommendations based on them are presented in the form of a report. Most of the research results are presented to two groups - managers of firms and specialist researchers. Two separate reports will be prepared as these groups have different information needs and goals. The first is a fully documented technical report, the second is an abbreviated report containing the main findings, conclusions and recommendations from the first report.

It was said above that most companies conduct market research with the help of specialized research agencies. To ensure the quality of such research, these agencies will be able to conduct all of the above types of research and act as executors.

In addition to fulfilling one-off orders from client firms, large agencies regularly collect systematic data in a specific area of marketing. The results of such surveys are always sent to subscribers in the form of a standard report. An example of this is the UK-based newsletter Inxetory Audit of Retail Sales, which publishes retail inventory data. In many cases, this newsletter is also known as the Nielsen Index after its founder.

The management of any manufacturer, depending on the market situation, the nature of the goals and objectives and the established strategy, what marketing research and how to conduct it, what human and financial resources to use, what to do independently, what research to order from abroad needs to be decided what it is good to do. To save human and financial resources and achieve high results when conducting marketing research, it is necessary to conceptually see how this problem will look in the future.

The development of this concept allows us to identify ways of a more rational solution to marketing research, as well as to see it in all its complexity. This is even more important.

Conclusions.

When conducting comprehensive and large-scale marketing research, it is advisable to develop a research concept in which to explain the problem in detail, show the ways and means of solving it in the most effective way. On the basis of such a concept, it is possible to develop a research project, a method for its implementation, formulate tasks, collect, process and analyze information, develop proposals and recommendations.

1. The observational method of market research is carried out from the point of view of the product, competitors, the market itself and consumers. Observation method is the most widely used method of data collection in economic and social statistics. Observation, in turn, differs in a number of classification criteria. Textbooks and textbooks on economic statistics provide ample information in this regard.

2. On the basis of observations, information related to the object or process under study can be obtained in bulk or selectively. Mass surveillance is based on the study of all the nodes of a complex. Such monitoring usually requires a lot of time and money, and the results serve to meet cross-sectoral needs. For example, registration of the population, registration of industrial and commercial enterprises in the relevant field, etc.

3. When developing a monitoring plan, it is necessary to define important descriptions of the situation and conditions in which the activities of the controlled persons take place, i. E. decide when and where to monitor.

Below is a summary of qualitative research methods such as in-depth interviews, protocol analysis, projection method, and physiological measurements. An in-depth interview is demonstrated by a qualified interviewer who asks a group of respondents research questions to understand why they behave in one way or another or what they think about a particular problem. The respondent is asked questions about the topic being studied and he / she can answer these questions. "Why did you answer that way?", "Can you substantiate your point of view?" asks questions like.

The first task in choosing a marketing research method is to become familiar with some of the methods that can be used in gathering marketing information. The most appropriate of these methods is then selected based on the availability of resources.

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